

Combining Distributed Queuing with energy harvesting to enable perpetual distributed data collection applications

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents, models and evaluates EH-DQ (Energy Harvesting-aware Distributed Queuing), a novel MAC protocol that combines Distributed Queuing (DQ) with Energy Harvesting (EH) to address data collection applications in industrial scenarios using long-range and low-power wireless communication technologies. We model the MAC protocol operation using a Markov chain and evaluate its ability to successfully transmit data without depleting the energy stored at the end-devices. In particular, we compare the performance and energy consumption of EH-DQ with that of TDMA (Time Division Multiple Access), which provides an upper limit in terms of data delivery, and EH-RDFS (EH-aware Reservation Dynamic Frame Slotted-ALOHA), which is an improved variation of FSA (Frame Slotted ALOHA). To evaluate the performance of these protocols we use two performance metrics: the delivery ratio and the time efficiency. The delivery ratio measures the ability to successfully transmit data without depleting the energy reserves, whereas the time efficiency measures the amount of data that can be transmitted in a certain amount of time. Results show that EH-DQ and TDMA perform close to the optimum in terms of data delivery, and both outperform EH-RDFS in terms of data delivery and time efficiency. Compared to TDMA, the time efficiency of EH-DQ is insensitive to the amount of harvested energy, making it more suitable for energy-constrained applications. Moreover, compared to TDMA, EH-DQ does not require updated network information to maintain a collision-free schedule, making it suitable for very dynamic networks.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1 Distributed data collection is an important use case
2 in the upcoming fourth Industrial revolution, as new
3 information will need to be extracted from equipment or
4 machines deployed within cities and factories in order
5 to automate or optimize processes. In a distributed data
6 collection application a gateway periodically requests
7 data from end devices and, upon request, all end devices
8 reply with their presence and the latest information
9 available. Such networks are dynamic in nature and are
10 formed by hundreds or thousands of devices, which are
11 typically powered using batteries and communicate with
12 the gateway using long-range and low-power wireless
13 communication technologies.

14 A root cause of energy expenditure in such scenarios
15 can be traced back to the MAC (Medium Access
16 Control) layer [1], which coordinates the access to
17 the wireless channel and determines when the radio

18 transceivers are powered on to transmit, listen, or
19 receive. There are two complementary strategies to
20 prolong the network lifetime: *i*) reduce the energy
21 consumption devoted to communications by means of
22 reducing packet collisions, packet overhearing, idle
23 listening and protocol overhead [2], [3], and *ii*) use
24 energy harvesting systems that collect the needed energy
25 from the environment [4], [5].

26 Motivated by this need, in this paper we focus
27 on data collection scenarios where hundreds or
28 thousands of end-devices, equipped with energy-
29 harvesters, periodically transmit a burst of data packets
30 upon request from a gateway. In such scenarios, a simple
31 Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) scheme would
32 allow every end-device to transmit without collisions.
33 However, this would come at the cost of requiring an
34 updated knowledge of the network topology in order
35 to maintain a collision-free schedule. In terms of delay
36 and energy consumption, this may be an expensive

37 procedure in highly dense networks. Contrarily, random
38 access protocols do not require topology knowledge and
39 their simplicity makes them ideal for simple and low-
40 cost end-devices, but the effects of collisions increase
41 energy expenditure reduce the network reliability.

42 An alternative to deterministic and random access
43 protocols to improve the performance of the network
44 and the energy consumption of end nodes is Distributed
45 Queuing (DQ). DQ ensures collision-free data transmis-
46 sions and offers a near optimum performance independ-
47 ent of the traffic load and the number of end-devices in
48 the network, completely avoiding congestion regardless
49 of how intense is the data traffic offered to the network
50 and the traffic pattern generated. The collision of data
51 packets is avoided by separating access requests from
52 the transmission of data. DQ dedicates a very short con-
53 tention window for access requests where the contention
54 is resolved using a tree-splitting algorithm [6]. Previ-
55 ous works related to DQ have analyzed throughput in
56 steady-state assuming that the end-devices generate data
57 packets following a random Poisson distribution. Under
58 this type of traffic, DQ achieves maximum throughput
59 when only 3 access request slots per frame are used,
60 regardless of the number of contending end-devices.

61 However, to the best of our knowledge, the design
62 and analysis of a MAC protocol based on DQ for
63 wireless networks with energy-harvesting has never
64 received attention. Despite the use of energy harvesting
65 may ideally provide infinite lifetime from the energy
66 perspective, it may not guarantee fully continuous
67 operation due to the high variability and unpredictability
68 of the energy harvesting process. Hence, an end-device
69 may enter temporarily in energy shortage when the
70 energy available is not enough for the operation of
71 the end-device. This fact needs to be considered for
72 the design of an energy-efficient MAC protocol based
73 on DQ which also take the energy-harvesting process
74 into account. This is the main motivation for the work
75 presented in this paper, which is an extension of the
76 work presented in [7] and [8], and aims to fill this gap
77 with the following contributions:

- 78 1. we propose Energy Harvesting-aware Distributed
79 Queuing (EH-DQ), a MAC protocol that com-
80 bines the Distributed Queuing (DQ) access tech-
81 nology with Energy Harvesting (EH). EH-DQ is
82 suitable for data collection networks where each
83 end-device is equipped with an energy harvester
84 and generates messages which have to be frag-
85 mented into small data packets to be transmitted
86 along the wireless channel. In EH-DQ, the end-
87 devices only become active to transmit data if the
88 energy available is above a predefined threshold.
- 89 2. through the use of a Markov chain model and
90 assuming an ideal wireless channel, we analyze
91 the evolution of the energy available in the
92 end-devices using EH-DQ and derive closed-
93 form equations to evaluate its performance in

94 terms of *data delivery ratio (DDR)* and *time*
95 *efficiency*. The DDR measures the ability of the
96 MAC protocol to successfully transmit data to the
97 gateway without depleting the energy reserves of
98 the end-devices, and the time efficiency measures
99 the amount of data that can be transmitted in a
100 certain amount of time.

- 101 3. we compare the performance of EH-DQ with that
102 of the upper-bound of an ideal TDMA protocol,
103 and with the performance of the EH-RDFSFA
104 protocol, which is based on the Dynamic Frame
105 Slotted-ALOHA protocol typically used in data
106 collection networks.

107 The remainder of this paper is organized as
108 follows. In Section 2, we present the related work to
109 MAC protocols and energy harvesting. In Section 3,
110 we describe the system model. In Section 4, we
111 summarize the operation of the EH-DQ, EH-RDFSFA
112 and TDMA protocols. In Section 5, we describe the
113 energy consumption model of EH-DQ. In Section 6,
114 we describe the performance metrics. In Section 7,
115 we present the analysis of the performance metrics.
116 Section 8 is devoted to evaluate the performance of
117 EH-DQ and validate the accuracy of the analysis
118 through comprehensive computer-based simulations.
119 The performance of EH-DQ, EH-RDFSFA and TDMA
120 are also compared in Section 8. Finally, Section 9
121 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

122 In this section, we present the related work, which
123 includes an overview of Distributed Queuing, Energy
124 Harvesting-Aware MAC protocols and, finally, the
125 Energy Harvesting process.

2.1. Distributed Queuing

126 DQ was first introduced as DQ Random Access
127 protocol (DQRAP) [9] for cable TV distribution, and
128 later adapted to different communication networks; to
129 wired centralized networks (Extended DQRAP [10],
130 Prioritized DQRAP [11]), satellite communications with
131 long propagation delays (Interleaved DQRAP [12]),
132 code-division multiple access for 3G cellular networks
133 (DQRAP/CDMA [13]), Wireless Local Area Networks
134 (DQCA [14]), cooperative communications (DQCOOP
135 [15]), wireless ad hoc networks (DQMAN [16]), and
136 body area networks (DQBAN [17]).

137 More recently, the work in [18, 19] proposes an
138 energy model of DQ for data collection scenarios. The
139 model is later validated experimentally in [20], which
140 demonstrates that DQ can indeed provide a network
141 performance that is independent of traffic load and
142 the number of end-devices in the network. Finally, in
143 [21] the authors demonstrate the use of DQ for active
144

145 RFID networks operating in the 433 MHz band. Both
 146 theoretical and experimental results show that DQ can
 147 also reduce energy consumption in more than 80% with
 148 respect to FSA.

149 2.2. Energy Harvesting-Aware MAC Protocols

150 The majority of work related to MAC protocols
 151 with energy harvesting focuses on slotted-ALOHA
 152 [22], Carrier Sense-Multiple Access (CSMA) [23] and
 153 Dynamic Frame Slotted-ALOHA (DFSA) [24]. In
 154 particular, the FSA and DFSA protocols have been
 155 proposed in the past [25, 26, 27] for data collection
 156 scenarios with energy harvesting where each end-device
 157 has just one data packet to transmit per request to the
 158 gateway. Results show that DFSA outperforms FSA in
 159 terms of delay when it is optimally configured, i.e., the
 160 frame length is adjusted to the number of contenders in
 161 every frame.

162 More recently, the Energy Harvesting-aware Reser-
 163 vation DFSA protocol (EH-RDFSA) was proposed by
 164 the authors in [28] to improve the performance of DFSA
 165 when the end-devices generate messages fragmented
 166 into small packets. Results show that EH-RDFSA out-
 167 performs DFSA by letting end-devices reserve the chan-
 168 nel, thus avoiding the need to compete for the channel
 169 for each newly generated fragment of the same message.
 170 Unfortunately, in order to minimize the probability of
 171 collision, all these variants of slotted-ALOHA require
 172 to adapt dynamically the frame length by estimating
 173 the number of contending end-devices, which may be
 174 difficult in highly dense networks where the end-devices
 175 may fall eventually in energy shortage.

176 2.3. Energy Harvesting process

177 Regarding the analytical modeling of the energy
 178 harvesting process, several research works have used
 179 different probability distributions to model energy
 180 sources. The work in [29] shows that no single
 181 probability distribution can fit all the empirical datasets
 182 of solar energy. The work in [30] shows that piezo-
 183 electric energy can be modeled by the generalized
 184 Markovian model, while solar energy can be modeled
 185 by a stationary Markovian model. The work in [31]
 186 proposes an analytical model in which the energy
 187 harvested in a time slot (of several seconds or minutes) is
 188 a random variable D . For mathematical tractability, the
 189 authors assume that D takes one of M discrete values
 190 $[d_1, \dots, d_M]$ with probability $[p_1, \dots, p_M]$. In this work,
 191 we use the approach of [31] and consider a probability
 192 distribution of the discrete exponential families (e.g.,
 193 binomial, geometric) to model the energy harvested in
 194 a time interval T_R .

3. SYSTEM MODEL

195 In this section, we present the system model, which
 196 encompasses the network topology and the data
 197 generation, as well as the process that end-devices
 198 follow to harvest, store and consume energy.

199 3.1. Network and Data Model

200 We consider a wireless network in star topology formed
 201 by one coordinator (or gateway) and n end-devices
 202 in the communication range of the coordinator, as
 203 shown in Figure 1. Each end-device is equipped with
 204 a radio-transceiver, a micro-controller, several sensors,
 205 an energy harvester and an energy storage device
 206 (ESD). As depicted in Figure 2, the coordinator gathers
 207 data (e.g., measurements) from the end-devices by
 208 initiating periodic Data Collection Rounds (DCR). Each
 209 DCR starts when the coordinator broadcasts a Request
 210 for Data (RFD) packet, once every T_R seconds. In
 211 the k -th DCR, each end-device has a number $l(k)$
 212 of new data packets ready to be transmitted to the
 213 coordinator. The data process $l(k)$ can be modeled as a
 214 discrete random variable with probability mass function
 215 $p_j = \Pr\{l(k) = j\}$ with $j \in \{1, 2, \dots\}$. The value of
 216 $l(k)$ is considered to be identically and independently
 217 distributed (i.i.d.) over all end-devices and DCRs. We
 218 assume that the data packets have a common and
 219 constant length.

220 At the beginning of the k -th DCR, an end-device
 221 enters into *active mode* to transmit data if the energy
 222 available in its ESD is above a predefined energy
 223 threshold. Otherwise, the end-device remains in *sleep*
 224 *mode* waiting for the next DCR. In the example of
 225 Figure 2, end-devices 1, 2, and 4 have enough energy
 226 to become active in the k -th DCR, while end-device 3
 227 remains in sleep mode. In the $(k + 1)$ -th DCR, end-
 228 devices 2, 3, and 4 become active, while end-device 1
 229 remains in sleep mode.

230 In this section, we describe the MAC protocols
 231 considered: TDMA, EH-RDFSA [28], and the EH-DQ
 232 protocol proposed in this paper.

233 The k -th DCR is formed by a sequence of F_k frames
 234 where each end-device in active mode transmits data to
 235 the coordinator according to the rules of the adopted
 236 MAC protocol. The coordinator broadcasts a feedback

Figure 1. Wireless network with energy harvesting capabilities in star topology.

Figure 2. Sequence of data collection rounds with end-devices equipped with energy harvesters.

237 packet (FBP) or beacon at the end of each frame to
 238 enable the synchronization of the active end-devices and
 239 to inform about the number of slots of the next frame
 240 depending on the MAC layer. An active end-device
 241 attempts to transmit its $l(k)$ data packets, one-by-one
 242 sequentially in time, as long as it has enough energy in
 243 its ESD. During the k -th DCR, an end-device enters into
 244 *sleep mode* when it either succeeds in transmitting the
 245 last of the $l(k)$ data packets or falls in energy shortage.
 246 Therefore, the k -th DCR finishes when all the active
 247 end-devices have entered into sleep mode. We assume
 248 that the duration $T_C(k)$ of the k -th DCR is much shorter
 249 than the time T_R between any two consecutive DCRs
 250 (i.e., $T_C(k) \ll T_R$ for all k) to ensure that successive
 251 DCRs do not overlap.

252 We consider that if an end-device fails to transmit
 253 one or more data packets due to energy shortage in any
 254 given DCR, those data packets are discarded and they
 255 are not transmitted in subsequent DCRs. This scenario
 256 represents very well applications where a number of
 257 sensors is transmitting data and some packets can be
 258 lost or not transmitted without seriously affecting the
 259 application. Just as an example, a meter reader in a
 260 smart grid may fail to transmit one reading of the
 261 energy consumption, even though the next reading will
 262 implicitly include this information. Therefore, no re-
 263 transmission of a failed data packet would be needed.

264 In order to focus the study on the performance of
 265 the MAC layer, we assume that all packets are always

266 transmitted without errors induced by the wireless
 267 channel. We assume that there is no capture effect, i.e.,
 268 when two or more data packets collide, none of the
 269 packets involved in the collision can be decoded by the
 270 coordinator. The inclusion of transmission errors and
 271 capture effect constitutes part of our future work.

272 3.2. Energy Storage Model

273 The amount of energy stored in the ESD of an end-
 274 device can be modeled as a random variable which
 275 depends on the harvested energy and the energy
 276 consumed by the end-device throughout the DCRs.
 277 The energy stored in the ESD of the i -th end-device
 278 is denoted by $E_{ESD,i} \in \{0, 1\delta, 2\delta, \dots, N\delta\}$, where δ
 279 [Joule] is referred to as *energy unit*, and N is the
 280 normalized capacity of the ESD. The end-device enters
 281 into active mode if the energy in its ESD at the
 282 beginning of the k -th DCR, denoted by $E_{ESD,i}(k)$,
 283 is above a certain energy threshold $E_{thr} = \varepsilon_{thr}\delta$,
 284 with $\varepsilon_{thr} \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1\}$. The probability that
 285 an end-device can take part in the k -th DCR is called
 286 activation probability, denoted by $p_{active}(k)$, which can
 287 be expressed as

$$p_{active}(k) = \Pr \{E_{ESD,i}(k) > E_{thr}\}. \quad (1)$$

288 The energy threshold ε_{th} must be selected so as to
 289 maximize performance.

290 3.3. Energy Harvesting Model

291 The energy harvester of the i -th end-device captures an
 292 amount of energy, denoted by $E_{H,i}(k)$, for the time
 293 interval T_R between any two consecutive DCRs ($k -$
 294 1)-th and k -th, which can be expressed as

$$E_{H,i}(k) = \int_{T_R} P_{H,i}(t) dt, \quad (2)$$

295 where $P_{H,i}(t)$ is the instantaneous electrical power
 296 delivered by the energy harvester.

297 The harvested energy $E_{H,i}(k)$ has been modeled
 298 as a discrete random variable with a probability
 299 mass function $q_j = \Pr\{E_{H,i}(k) = j\delta\}$ with $j \in$
 300 $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, N_H\}$ energy units, which depends on the
 301 characteristics of the energy source and N_H is the
 302 maximum number of energy units that can be captured
 303 by the energy harvester. $E_{H,i}(k)$ is considered to be
 304 i.i.d. with regard to other end-devices and DCRs.

305 The *energy harvesting rate*, denoted by \bar{E}_H , is
 306 defined as the average harvested energy of an end-
 307 device during the time T_R between the beginning of two
 308 consecutive DCRs, which can be expressed as

$$\bar{E}_H = \mathbb{E}[E_{H,i}(k)]. \quad (3)$$

309 We assume that the dynamics of the energy harvesting
 310 process is slower than the contention process in a DCR.
 311 Therefore, we consider that the amount of energy that
 312 is harvested within the duration $T_c(k)$ of the k -th
 313 contention process is negligible with respect to $E_{H,i}(k)$,
 314 and it is not immediately available to be used during
 315 the contention process. Consequently, all the harvested
 316 energy $E_{H,i}(k)$ is ready to be used by an end-device at
 317 the beginning of the k -th DCR.

318 3.4. Energy Consumption Model

319 Regarding energy consumption, the end-devices can be
 320 in four different modes of operation: (i) transmitting
 321 a packet; (ii) receiving; (iii) standby, or (iv) sleeping.
 322 The associated power consumption are ρ_{tx} , ρ_{rx} , ρ_{stby} ,
 323 or ρ_{sleep} , respectively. We assume that the energy
 324 required to switch between sleep and active modes
 325 (*i.e.*, transmitting, receiving) is negligible. In sleep
 326 mode, the radio interface is fully disabled, and thus, the
 327 end-devices consume the lowest power consumption.

328 In Section 5, we use the power consumption levels
 329 to formulate the analytical expressions required to
 330 compute the energy consumed by an end-device in a
 331 given frame by accounting for the energy used in all
 332 the communication phases (where the end-device is
 333 transmitting, in standby or receiving) depending on the
 334 type of frame.

4. MEDIUM ACCESS CONTROL PROTOCOLS

335 In this section, we describe the MAC protocols
 336 considered: TDMA, EH-RDFSFA [28], and the EH-DQ
 337 protocol proposed in this paper.

338 4.1. Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA)

339 In TDMA, each frame is composed of a fixed number
 340 m_R of reserved slots that is equal to the number n of
 341 end-devices in the network. Each slot is allocated to
 342 one end-device. An end-device that becomes active in the
 343 k -th DCR will transmit its $l(k)$ data packets in its
 344 reserved slot in $l(k)$ successive frames (one packet per
 345 frame) as long as the end-device has enough energy. The
 346 coordinator responds with an acknowledgment packet
 347 (ACK) to each data packet decoded successfully within
 348 the same slot where the data packet has been transmitted.
 349 The coordinator broadcasts a feedback packet (FBP)
 350 or beacon at the end of each frame to enable the
 351 synchronization of the active end-devices.

352 4.2. Energy Harvesting-aware Reservation 353 Dynamic FSA (EH-RDFSFA)

354 In EH-RDFSFA, each frame is composed of a variable
 355 number m_R of reserved slots and m_C contention slots.
 356 The number of reserved slots in the first frame is
 357 always 0. An end-device that becomes active in the k -
 358 th DCR randomly selects one of the contention slots
 359 in every frame to transmit the first of its data packets.
 360 A contention slot can be in one of three states: empty,
 361 if no packet has been transmitted in that slot; success,
 362 if only one packet has been transmitted; or collision,
 363 if more than one end-device has transmitted in that
 364 slot. When an end-device succeeds in transmitting the
 365 first packet in a given frame, one reserved slot will be
 366 allocated to the end-device for subsequent frames. The
 367 coordinator informs the end-device about the specific
 368 reserved slot with an ACK transmitted within the same
 369 slot where the data packet was transmitted. Then, the
 370 end-device transmits its other $l(k) - 1$ data packets in
 371 the reserved slot (one packet per frame) as long as it has
 372 enough energy. The coordinator responds with an ACK
 373 to each data packet decoded successfully in each slot.
 374 A reserved slot is released either once an end-device
 375 has transmitted all its data packets or enters in energy
 376 shortage. The header of every data packet includes a flag
 377 that indicates whether it is the last packet of the sequence
 378 of $l(k)$ packets to be transmitted in this DCR, and one
 379 field which informs about the energy available in the
 380 end-device. This information is used by the coordinator
 381 to calculate the number m_R of reserved slots in the
 382 next frame. In order to minimize $T_C(k)$, the coordinator
 383 adjusts the value of m_C to be equal to the number of
 384 active end-devices that contend to transmit their first
 385 data packet. The coordinator broadcasts a FBP at the end

Figure 3. DQ frame structure.

386 of each frame to inform about the values of m_R and m_C
 387 for the next frame.

388 4.3. Energy Harvesting-aware Distributed 389 Queuing (EH-DQ)

390 EH-DQ is the MAC protocol proposed in this work.
 391 In EH-DQ, the active end-devices request access to the
 392 channel in a short contention window at the beginning
 393 of each frame, thus confining collisions to a specific part
 394 of the frame. Collisions are resolved by using a tree-
 395 splitting algorithm [6] that organizes the end-devices
 396 into sub-groups to reduce the probability of collision
 397 per transmission attempt. When an end-device succeeds
 398 in transmitting its access request, it waits for its turn
 399 to transmit data in collision-free slots. Each frame of EH-
 400 DQ is divided in three parts as shown in Figure 3: (i)
 401 m contention slots devoted to the transmission of access
 402 request (ARS) packets, (ii) one collision-free slot for the
 403 transmission of a data packet, and (iii) a feedback packet
 404 (FBP). A guard time called Inter Frame Space (IFS)
 405 is left between reception and transmission modes to
 406 compensate propagation and processing delays and the
 407 time required to switch the radio transceivers between
 408 reception and transmission.

409 Every active end-device randomly selects one of the
 410 contention slots in every frame to transmit an ARS. Each
 411 ARS only contains one field (e.g., 1 byte) that indicates
 412 the number of data packets that must be transmitted by
 413 an end-device, i.e., the number l_R of collision-free slots
 414 to be reserved, which depends on the energy available
 415 in the end-device. Note that the ARS does not need to
 416 identify the end-device. Depending on whether the ARS
 417 collides or is successfully decoded by the coordinator,
 418 an end-device is queued into one of two logical and
 419 distributed queues:

420 1) The end-devices that have collided in a given
 421 contention slot when transmitting their ARS are queued
 422 into the *Collision Resolution Queue* (CRQ), sharing the
 423 same position in the queue. Note that after every frame,
 424 at most m new entries enter into the CRQ, being each
 425 one associated to each of the collisions that occurred in
 426 the last contention window. The length of the CRQ and
 427 the position of the end-devices in the CRQ is updated
 428 by executing the tree-splitting algorithm represented in
 429 Figure 4.a. Each node of the tree represents a frame of m
 430 contention slots ($m=3$ in the example), and the number
 431 in each contention slot denotes the number of end-
 432 devices that transmit an ARS in that slot. In every level

433 of the tree, an end-device transmits its ARS in only one
 434 frame until it succeeds in one level or enters in energy
 435 shortage. The algorithm works as follows. At frame 1,
 436 all the active end-devices contend. If two or more end-
 437 devices collide in a slot, a new frame is assigned only
 438 to the end-devices that caused the collision in order to
 439 reattempt access, and they are queued into the CRQ.
 440 Therefore, if there are k slots with collision in one frame
 441 of level d , then k new frames are scheduled in level
 442 $d + 1$, and k sub-groups of end-devices are queued into
 443 the CRQ. Once an end-device has entered in the CRQ,
 444 it will re-transmit its ARS in a given frame only if it
 445 has enough energy in its ESD and it occupies the first
 446 position in the CRQ; otherwise, the end-device enters in
 447 sleep mode and waits until it reaches the first position of
 448 the CRQ.

449 2) The end-devices that succeed in transmitting their
 450 ARS are queued into the *Data Transmission Queue*
 451 (DTQ). In principle, any queue discipline could be used
 452 to this end. For example, devices could enter into the
 453 DTQ following the same chronological order of the
 454 contention slots. Contrarily to the CRQ, in this case,
 455 every position of the DTQ is occupied by just one end-
 456 device. Indeed, an end-device occupies a number of
 457 positions in the DTQ that is equal to the number l_R
 458 of collision-free data slots reserved by the end-device for
 459 this particular DCR. When an end-device reaches the
 460 first position of the DTQ, it transmits its data packets
 461 in the collision-free slot of successive frames.

462 The CRQ and DTQ are represented at each end-
 463 device by 2 integer numbers per queue representing:
 464 1) the position of the end-device in the queue, and
 465 2) the total length of the queue. The length of the
 466 CRQ represents the number of sub-groups of end-
 467 devices waiting to re-transmit an ARS. The length of
 468 the DTQ represents the total number of collision-free
 469 slots reserved by the end-devices that have succeeded in
 470 transmitting their ARS and wait for their first collision-
 471 free slot.

472 The coordinator updates the length of the CRQ and
 473 DTQ at the end of each frame according to the following
 474 rules: 1) the length of the CRQ is incremented by the
 475 number of contention slots with collision; 2) if the CRQ
 476 was not empty in the previous frame, then its length
 477 is decremented by one; 3) the length of the DTQ is
 478 incremented by the total number of collision-free slots
 479 reserved in each frame; and 4) if the DTQ was not empty
 480 in the previous frame, then its length is decremented by
 481 one.

482 The coordinator broadcasts in every FBP: (i) the
 483 length of the CRQ (2 bytes); (ii) the length of the
 484 DTQ (2 bytes); and (iii) the state of the m contention
 485 slots (empty, success, or collision) and the number
 486 of collision-free slots reserved in every slot with one
 487 successful ARS (1 byte per contention slot). Using the
 488 information of the FBP, an end-device that transmitted
 489 an ARS can compute its position in the CRQ if it

490 collides, or its position in the DTQ if it succeeds. The
 491 positions in the CRQ and DTQ are always decremented
 492 by one at the end of each frame. Therefore, the end-
 493 devices only receive the FBP in those frames where
 494 they transmit either an ARS or a data packet, and they
 495 enter into sleep mode in those frames where they do not
 496 transmit either ARS or data, in order to save energy.

497 Figure 4 shows an example of the operation of EH-
 498 DQ. The contents of the slots and the lengths of the
 499 CRQ and DTQ in every frame are shown in Figure 4.a.
 500 The contents of both queues are shown in Figure 4.b. At
 501 frame 1, all the end-devices (d1 to d6) transmit an ARS:
 502 d1, d2 and d3 collide in slot 1; d4 succeeds in slot 2; d5
 503 and d6 collide in slot 3. Thus, d1, d2 and d3 enter in the
 504 first position of the CRQ; d4 enters in the first position
 505 of the DTQ reserving 1 collision-free slot; d5 and d6
 506 enter in the second position of the CRQ. At frame 2,
 507 d4 transmits its data packet (because it occupies the first
 508 position of the DTQ), and d1, d2 and d3 transmit an ARS
 509 (because they occupy the first position of the CRQ): d1
 510 and d2 collide and enter in the CRQ again; d3 succeeds
 511 and enters in the DTQ reserving 2 collision-free slots; d5
 512 and d6 move to the first position of the CRQ. At frame
 513 3, d5 and d6 transmit an ARS, collide, and enter in the
 514 second position of the CRQ again; d1 and d2 move to the
 515 first position of the CRQ; and d3 transmits its first data
 516 packet. At frame 4, d3 transmits its second data packet;
 517 d1 and d2 transmit an ARS, succeed, and enter in the
 518 DTQ reserving 1 collision-free slot each; and d5 and
 519 d6 move to the first position of the CRQ. The process
 520 continues until the end of the DCR.

5. ENERGY CONSUMPTION MODEL USING EH-DQ

521 In EH-DQ, every time that an end-device transmits
 522 an ARS in a certain frame of a DCR, it consumes a
 523 constant amount of energy, denoted by E_{ARS} [Joule],
 524 which accounts for the energy used in the following
 525 communication phases: (i) the end-device transmits the
 526 ARS in 1 contention slot, (ii) it remains in standby mode
 527 in the other $m - 1$ contention slots and in the collision-
 528 free slot, and (iii) it receives the FBP. Then, E_{ARS} can
 529 be formulated as

$$E_{ARS} = \rho_{tx}T_{ARS} + (m - 1)\rho_{stby}T_{ARS} + \quad (4)$$

$$\rho_{stby}T_{data} + \rho_{rx}T_{FBP}, \quad (5)$$

530 where T_{ARS} , T_{data} and T_{FBP} are the duration of
 531 a contention slot, a collision-free slot, and the time
 532 of transmission of a FBP, respectively; and ρ_{tx} , ρ_{rx}
 533 and ρ_{stby} are the power consumption in transmission,
 534 reception and standby mode, respectively.

535 Every time that an end-device transmits one data
 536 packet in a certain frame of a DCR, it consumes a
 537 constant amount of energy, denoted by E_{data} [Joule],
 538 which accounts for the energy used in the following

539 communication phases: (i) the end-device remains in
 540 standby mode in m contention slots, (ii) it transmits data
 541 in the collision-free slot, and (iii) it receives the FBP.
 542 Then, E_{data} can be formulated as

$$E_{data} = m\rho_{stby}T_{ARS} + \rho_{tx}T_{data} + \rho_{rx}T_{FBP}. \quad (6)$$

543 We assume that the energy consumed by an end-
 544 device in those frames where it is in sleep mode is
 545 negligible. For convenience, we normalize these energy
 546 consumption to $E_{ARS} = 1\delta$ and $E_{data} \approx K\delta$, where
 547 K is a positive integer number. Therefore, an end-device
 548 consumes 1 and K energy units δ when it transmits an
 549 ARS or a data packet in a frame, respectively.

6. PERFORMANCE METRICS

550 The *data delivery ratio* (DDR) is defined as the ratio
 551 between the number of data packets that are successfully
 552 transmitted to the coordinator in the k -th DCR, and
 553 the number of data packets ready to be transmitted
 554 at the beginning of the DCR. The DDR measures the
 555 ability of the MAC protocol to successfully deliver long
 556 data messages fragmented in small packets from the
 557 end-devices to the coordinator in every DCR without
 558 depleting their ESD.

559 The *time efficiency* is defined as the ratio between the
 560 duration of all the data packets successfully transmitted
 561 to the coordinator in the k -th DCR, and the time $T_C(k)$
 562 required to complete the DCR. This value measures the
 563 probability that one slot allocated by the MAC layer
 564 during a DCR is successfully used. Therefore, the time
 565 efficiency is an indicator of the *data collection rate*,
 566 which can be obtained by dividing the time efficiency
 567 by the duration of a slot.

568 Due to the fluctuations of the harvested energy, the
 569 limited capacity of the ESDs, and collisions, both DDR
 570 and time efficiency may be lower than 1. Since the
 571 use of energy harvesters potentially allows for perpetual
 572 operation, it is interesting to analyze the performance
 573 metrics when the system is in *steady-state*, i.e., for a
 574 DCR with large index k .

7. ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE METRICS

575 In order to derive an analytic model to compute the DDR
 576 and the time efficiency in steady-state for EH-DQ, we
 577 need to evaluate the steady-state probability distribution
 578 of the energy available in the ESDs at the beginning
 579 of a DCR, which depends on the energy harvesting
 580 process, the random slot selection in every frame, the
 581 tree splitting process, and the number of data packets
 582 transmitted by each end-device in previous DCRs.
 583 Given that the number of end-devices that contend in
 584 every frame depends on the energy available in the

(b) Contents of CRQ and DTQ in each frame of the process

Figure 4. Example of EH-DQ with 6 end-devices (d1 to d6) and 3 contention slots: (a) tree-splitting algorithm, and (b) contents of the CRQ and DTQ in each frame.

585 ESD at each end-device, deriving the exact steady-state
 586 probability distribution is not an easy task. However,
 587 if we adjust the value of the energy threshold ε_{th}
 588 (1) to guarantee that all the end-devices that become
 589 active (n_1) in a DCR will have enough energy to
 590 contend in a certain number of levels, assuming that the
 591 number of end-devices that fall in energy shortage in a
 592 DCR is negligible, we can consider that the probability
 593 that an end-device succeeds in transmitting an ARS
 594 packet in one frame of any level of the contention tree
 595 basically depends on the value of n_1 , the number of
 596 slots per frame, and the level number where the device
 597 contents. Consequently, we can evaluate the steady-state
 598 probability distribution of the energy available in the
 599 ESDs by analyzing the evolution of the energy of a
 600 single ESD, which is an approximation that neglects the
 601 interactions among the ESDs of different end-devices.

602 In this section, we derive an analytic model for EH-
 603 DQ to compute the DDR and the time efficiency in
 604 steady-state. To this end, in Section 7.1 we first propose
 605 a discrete-time Markov chain model to analyze the
 606 evolution of the energy available in the ESD of a given
 607 end-device. In Section 7.2, we derive the probability that
 608 an end-device succeeds in transmitting an ARS packet in
 609 one frame of a DCR. Finally, we derive in Section 7.3

610 the steady-state probability distribution of the energy
 611 available in the ESDs at the beginning of a DCR, we
 612 formulate the DDR in Section 7.4 and the time efficiency
 613 in Section 7.5.

614 7.1. Markov Chain Model

615 The evolution of the energy available in the ESD of
 616 an end-device can be modeled with the discrete-time
 617 Markov chain shown in Figure 5. Each state in the chain
 618 is defined by $\{e(t), d(t)\}$, where $e(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$
 619 is a stochastic process that represents the number of
 620 energy units δ available in the ESD at time t ; and
 621 $d(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, N - K\}$ is a stochastic process that
 622 represents that either an end-device is in sleep mode
 623 when $d(t) = 0$, or the level number in the contention
 624 tree where an end-device transmits an ARS when $d(t) \in$
 625 $\{1, \dots, N - K\}$. Recall that in every level of the tree, an
 626 end-device transmits an ARS in only one frame. Note
 627 that the state transitions in the Markov chain do not
 628 occur at fixed time intervals.

629 The Markov chain is characterized by a transition
 630 matrix $P = [p_{ij}]$, where each element p_{ij} is the one-step
 631 transition probability defined as

$$p_{ij} = \Pr \{e(t+1) = e_j, d(t+1) = d_j | e(t) = e_i, d(t) = d_i\} . \quad (7)$$

Figure 5. Generalized state transition diagram of the Markov chain that models the evolution of the energy available in an ESD using EH-DQ.

632 An end-device that has successfully transmitted all its
633 data packets or entered in energy shortage in a DCR,
634 remains in sleep mode (i.e., in a state with $d_i = 0$)
635 until the next DCR starts. At the beginning of a DCR,
636 the number ε_H of energy units harvested in the last
637 T_R interval is added to the energy in the ESD, i.e.,
638 $e_j = e_i + \varepsilon_H$. Then, if the number of energy units
639 available in the ESD is above the threshold ε_{th} , i.e., $e_j \in$
640 $\{\varepsilon_{th} + 1, \dots, N\}$, the state of the end-device changes
641 from sleep ($e_i, 0$) to active mode ($e_j, 1$). Otherwise,
642 if the number e_j of energy units in the ESD is below
643 or equal to ε_{th} , the end-device makes a transition from
644 state ($e_i, 0$) to state ($e_j, 0$) and remains in sleep mode.
645 The transition probability from state ($e_i, 0$) to any state
646 (e_j, d_j) at the beginning of a DCR can be expressed as
647 where q_{ε_H} is the probability that an end-device
648 harvests a number ε_H of energy units, being $\varepsilon_H = e_j -$
649 e_i with $e_i \leq e_j$.

650 Once an end-device becomes active at the beginning
651 of a DCR, it will transmit an ARS packet in one frame of
652 every successive level of the contention tree until either
653 it succeeds or its ESD falls below $(1 + K)$ energy units.
654 Recall that an end-device consumes 1 energy unit when
655 transmits an ARS, and K energy units when transmits a
656 data packet.

657 If the end-device does not succeed in transmitting
658 an ARS in one frame of level $d_i \in \{1, \dots, N - K\}$,
659 it can make two possible transitions: (i) to state
660 $(e_i - 1, d_i + 1)$, if the end-device has enough energy
661 to re-transmit an ARS in the next level and to transmit
662 one or more data packets, i.e., $e_i \in \{2 + K, \dots, N\}$; or
663 (ii) to state $(K, 0)$, if the end-device has not enough
664 energy to re-transmit an ARS and a data packet, i.e.,
665 $e_i = 1 + K$.

666 Once an end-device succeeds in transmitting an ARS
667 in one frame of level d_i , which happens with probability

$$p_{ij} = \begin{cases} q_{\varepsilon_H}, & \text{if } (e_i \leq e_j) \text{ and } (e_j \leq \varepsilon_{th}) \text{ and } (d_j = 0) \\ q_{\varepsilon_H}, & \text{if } (e_i \leq e_j) \text{ and } (\varepsilon_{th} < e_j < N) \text{ and } (d_j = 1) \\ 1 - \sum_{k=0}^{N-1-e_i} q_k, & \text{if } (e_i < e_j) \text{ and } (e_j = N) \text{ and } (d_j = 1) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

668 $p_{s,d}$ with $d = d_i$ (derived in Section 7.2), the end-
 669 device will transmit a number $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, l_{max}\}$ of
 670 data packets in the collision-free slot of subsequent
 671 frames. The maximum value l_{max} is limited by the
 672 energy available in the ESD, i.e., $l_{max} = \lfloor \frac{e_i - 1}{K} \rfloor$.
 673 Thus, the end-device makes the following transitions
 674 from state (e_i, d_i) : (i) to states $(e_i - 1 - lK, 0)$ with
 675 probability $p_{s,d} \cdot p_l$ for $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, l_{max} - 1\}$, or (ii)
 676 to state $(e_i - 1 - l_{max}K, 0)$ with probability $p_{s,d} \cdot$
 677 $\left(1 - \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}-1} p_l\right)$ for $l \in \{l_{max}, \dots, L\}$, where p_l is
 678 the probability that an end-device has a number $l \in$
 679 $\{1, 2, \dots, L\}$ of data packets ready to transmit at the
 680 beginning of a DCR. Consequently, the transition
 681 probability from state (e_i, d_i) to state (e_j, d_j) with $d_i \in$
 682 $\{1, 2, \dots, N - K\}$ can be formulated as in Equation (9).

683 7.2. Probability of Success in one Frame

684 The probability that an end-device succeeds in
 685 transmitting an ARS packet in one frame of level $d \in$
 686 $\{1, 2, \dots, N - K\}$, denoted by $p_{s,d}$, can be expressed as

$$p_{s,d} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right)^{n_d - 1}, \quad (10)$$

687 where m is the number slots per frame and n_d is the
 688 number of end-devices which contend in one frame of
 689 level d .

690 In the first frame of a steady-state DCR, i.e., in level
 691 $d = 1$, the number n_1 of end-devices that contend is
 692 equal to the average number of end-devices that become
 693 active, which can be expressed as $n_1 = n \cdot p_{active}^{SS}$,
 694 where n is the total number of end-devices and p_{active}^{SS}
 695 is the activation probability in steady-state, i.e., for large
 696 index k of DCR, defined as

$$p_{active}^{SS} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} p_{active}(k). \quad (11)$$

697 We can assume that all the end-devices that become
 698 active in a steady-state DCR will have enough energy
 699 to contend until they succeed in transmitting an ARS.
 700 Note that this can be guaranteed by properly adjusting
 701 the value of the threshold ε_{th} . Under this assumption,
 702 the value of n_d for $d > 1$ can be derived as follows.
 703 First, the probability that k of n_d end-devices transmit
 704 in the same slot of a frame, denoted by $p_s(k)$, can be
 705 calculated as

$$p_s(k) = \binom{n_d}{k} \left(\frac{1}{m}\right)^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right)^{n_d - k}, \quad (12)$$

706 and the average number of empty, success, and
 707 collision slots in that frame can be calculated as $S_d^E =$
 708 $m \cdot p_s(0)$, $S_d^S = m \cdot p_s(1)$, and $S_d^C = m - S_d^E - S_d^S$,
 709 respectively.

710 As described in Section 4.3, if there are S_d^C slots
 711 with collision in one frame of level d , then $F_{d+1} = S_d^C$
 712 new frames are scheduled in level $d + 1$, where each
 713 new frame in level $d + 1$ is assigned only to the sub-
 714 group of end-devices that caused a collision in the same
 715 specific slot of level d . The average number of end-
 716 devices that succeed in one frame of level d , denoted
 717 by n_d^S , is equal to the average number S_d^S of slots with
 718 success. Therefore, the average number of end-devices
 719 that collide in one frame of level d , denoted by n_d^C ,
 720 can be calculated as $n_d^C = n_d - S_d^S$. Since we assume
 721 that the n_d^C end-devices have enough energy, they will
 722 contend again in F_{d+1} new frames of level $d + 1$. Then,
 723 the average number of end-devices that contend in one
 724 frame of level $d + 1$ can be calculated as

725 The probability that an end-device succeeds in trans-
 726 mitting an ARS in one frame of every level of the con-
 727 tentation tree (10) is represented in Figure 6a. It has been
 728 evaluated with $m \in \{3, 10\}$, $n \in \{10 \cdot m, 100 \cdot m\}$,
 729 $p_{active}^{SS} = 1$, and considering that all the end-devices
 730 that become active in a DCR have enough energy to
 731 contend until they succeed in transmitting their ARS
 732 packet in the DCR regardless of the energy harvesting
 733 rate and the capacity of the ESDs. Results show a tight
 734 match between analytic and simulated results. As it
 735 could be expected, the value of $p_{s,d}$ is close to 0
 736 for low values of d , especially when the number m of slots
 737 is low and the number n of end-devices is high.

738 In order to set an appropriate value for the threshold
 739 ε_{th} which minimizes the probability that an end-
 740 device enters in energy shortage before it succeeds in
 741 transmitting an ARS, it is necessary to calculate the
 742 average number of frames where an end-device has to
 743 contend until it succeeds, denoted by $\mathbb{E}[d]$, which can
 744 be expressed as

$$\mathbb{E}[d] = \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} d \cdot p_{s,d} \cdot \prod_{i=1}^{d-1} (1 - p_{s,i}). \quad (14)$$

745 The value of $\mathbb{E}[d]$ is represented in Figure 6b as
 746 a function of the number of end-devices. It has been
 747 evaluated by considering $m \in \{5, 10, 20\}$. As it could
 748 be expected, the value of $\mathbb{E}[d]$ increases with n for a
 749 given value of m . The energy threshold needs to be
 750 adjusted as $\varepsilon_{th} \geq \mathbb{E}[d]$ depending on the values of m

$$p_{ij} = \begin{cases} (1 - p_{s,d}), & \text{if } (e_i \geq 2 + K) \text{ and } (e_j = e_i - 1) \text{ and } (d_j = d_i + 1) \\ (1 - p_{s,d}), & \text{if } (e_i = 1 + K) \text{ and } (e_j = K) \text{ and } (d_j = 0) \\ p_{s,d} \cdot p_l, & \text{if } (1 \leq l < l_{max}) \text{ and } (e_j = e_i - 1 - Kl) \text{ and } (d_j = 0) \\ p_{s,d} \cdot \left(1 - \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}-1} p_l\right), & \text{if } (l \geq l_{max}) \text{ and } (e_j = e_i - 1 - Kl_{max}) \text{ and } (d_j = 0) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

$$n_{d+1} = \frac{n_d - S_d^S}{F_{d+1}} = \frac{n_d - n_d \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right)^{n_d-1}}{m - m \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right)^{n_d} - n_d \left(1 - \frac{1}{m}\right)^{n_d-1}}. \quad (13)$$

Figure 6. Probability that an end-device succeeds in transmitting an ARS in one frame of every level of the tree. Average number of levels where an end-device contends until it succeeds in transmitting an ARS in a DCR.

751 and n . For example, for a network of 1000 end-devices,
 752 the minimum energy threshold must be close to 5, 4, or
 753 3 energy units when m is 5, 10, or 20 slots, respectively.

754 7.3. Steady-State Probability Distributions

755 As it can be observed in Figure 5, when $p_d > 0$
 756 for $d \in \{1, 2, \dots, N - K\}$, $q_0 > 0$ and $q_1 > 0$, the
 757 Markov chain is aperiodic and any state of the Markov
 758 chain can be reached from any other state with non-
 759 zero probability, and therefore the Markov chain is
 760 irreducible [32].

761 Since the Markov chain is irreducible and aperiodic,
 762 and thus ergodic, it admits a unique steady-state
 763 probability distribution [32], denoted by $\pi = [\pi_{e,d}]$,
 764 which can be expressed as

$$\pi_{e,d} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Pr \{e(t) = e, d(t) = d\}, \quad (15)$$

765 and satisfies that

$$(P' - I) \pi' = 0, \quad (16)$$

766 where P is the transition matrix and I is the identity
 767 matrix. Equation (16) can be solved for π by calculating

768 the eigenvector of P' that corresponds to an eigenvalue
 769 equal to 1. The steady-state probability distribution π is
 770 equal to the eigenvector with its elements normalized to
 771 sum one.

772 Recall that the transition matrix P depends on $p_{s,d}$
 773 (10), which also depends on p_{active}^{SS} (11). On the other
 774 hand, p_{active}^{SS} can be expressed from the steady-state
 775 probability distribution of the energy available in the
 776 ESD at the beginning of a DCR, denoted by $\pi^B =$
 777 $[\pi_{e,d}^B]$, as follows

$$p_{active}^{SS} = \pi_{\varepsilon_{thr}+1,1}^B + \dots + \pi_{N,1}^B = \sum_{e=\varepsilon_{thr}+1}^N \pi_{e,1}^B. \quad (17)$$

778 Note that all the values of π^B are zero for $d \in$
 779 $\{2, \dots, N - K\}$. This is due to the fact that at the
 780 beginning of a DCR an end-device can only reach either
 781 states $(e, 0)$ with $e \in \{0, 1, \dots, \varepsilon_{th}\}$ or $(e, 1)$ with $e \in$
 782 $\{\varepsilon_{th} + 1, \dots, N\}$. Since an end-device is in sleep mode
 783 before a DCR starts, π^B can be expressed as

$$\pi^B = \pi^S P, \quad (18)$$

784 where $\pi^S = [\pi_{e,d}^S]$ is the steady-state probability
 785 distribution conditioned on being in sleep mode, which

786 is calculated as

$$\pi_{e,d}^S = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi_{e,0}}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \pi_{i,0}}, & \text{if } (d = 0) \\ 0, & \text{if } (1 \leq d \leq N - K) \end{cases}. \quad (19)$$

787 Finally, we compute the steady-state probability dis-
 788 tributions as follows. Firstly, we build the transition ma-
 789 trix P by setting the steady-state activation probability
 790 to a test value of 0, i.e., $p_{active-test}^{SS} = 0$. Secondly, we
 791 solve equations (16), (19), and (18) to calculate π , π^S ,
 792 and π^B , respectively. Thirdly, we compute the analytic
 793 value of p_{active}^{SS} (17) by using π^B . And finally, we check
 794 the relative error between the test and analytic values
 795 of the activation probability. These steps are repeated
 796 iteratively by increasing $p_{active-test}^{SS}$ until the error is
 797 below 0.1%, which indicates that it satisfies (16), (19)
 798 and (18), and the results obtained for π , π^S , and π^B are
 799 correct.

800 7.4. Data Delivery Ratio

801 Once the steady-state probability distribution π^B of the
 802 energy available in the ESD at the beginning of a DCR is
 803 computed, we can formulate the expression to calculate
 804 the *data delivery ratio* in steady-state for EH-DQ as
 805 follows

$$DDR = \frac{\mathbb{E}[N_S]}{\mathbb{E}[N_R]} = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^L \mathbb{E}[N_d(l)] \cdot p_l}{\sum_{l=1}^L l \cdot p_l}, \quad (20)$$

806 where $\mathbb{E}[N_S]$ is the average number of data packets
 807 that are successfully transmitted to the coordinator in
 808 a DCR, $\mathbb{E}[N_R]$ is the average number of packets
 809 ready to be transmitted at the beginning of the
 810 DCR, and $\mathbb{E}[N_d(l)]$ is the average number of packets
 811 successfully transmitted by an end-device when it has
 812 $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$ packets ready at the beginning of the
 813 DCR, which can be expressed as

814 Recall that an end-device which enters in active mode
 815 re-transmits an ARS packet in subsequent frames until
 816 it is successfully decoded by the coordinator. Then, the
 817 end-device transmits a number l_R of data packets which
 818 depends on the number l of packets ready, the amount
 819 of energy e available at the beginning of the DCR,
 820 and the level number d where the ARS succeeds, i.e.,
 821 $l_R = \min(l, \lfloor \frac{e-d}{K} \rfloor)$.

822 7.5. Time Efficiency

823 The *time efficiency* for EH-DQ, denoted by J_t , can be
 824 formulated as where $\mathbb{E}[N_E]$ is the average number of
 825 frames with the collision-free slot empty, i.e., frames
 826 which do not contain data. Since every active end-device
 827 transmits a number $l_R \geq 1$ of data packets, we can
 828 assume that once an end-device has first succeeded in
 829 transmitting an ARS in a given frame, every frame until

830 the end of the DCR contains data. Therefore, $\mathbb{E}[N_E]$ can
 831 be approximated as the average number of frames where
 832 an end-device contends until it succeeds, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[N_E] \approx$
 833 $\mathbb{E}[d]$ (14). Since $\mathbb{E}[d] \ll \mathbb{E}[N_S]$, the expression of J_t
 834 can be approximated as

$$J_t \simeq \frac{T_{data}}{mT_{ARS} + T_{data} + T_{FBP}}, \quad (23)$$

835 where recall that T_{ARS} , T_{data} and T_{FBP} are the
 836 duration of a contention slot, a collision-free slot, and
 837 the time of transmission of a FBP, respectively.

8. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

838 In this section, we evaluate the performance of EH-
 839 DQ, in terms of the DDR and the time efficiency, and
 840 compare it with the performance of TDMA and EH-
 841 RDFSFA. While in the theoretical model of EH-DQ the
 842 steady-state probability distribution of the energy in the
 843 ESDs is calculated by analyzing the evolution of the
 844 energy of a single ESD, which is an approximation of
 845 the actual model, the simulation does not neglect the
 846 interactions among the ESDs of different end-devices.

847 In the following sections, we first describe the
 848 considered scenario, and then discuss the numerical
 849 results to show how the performance is influenced by the
 850 energy threshold, the number of contention slots, and the
 851 energy harvesting rate.

852 8.1. Scenario

853 We consider a wireless network formed by 1 coordinator
 854 and a large number $n = 1000$ of end-devices. Each
 855 end-device periodically acquires measurements from a
 856 set of sensors and generates $L = 5$ data packets to be
 857 transmitted to the coordinator in every DCR. Each data
 858 packet has a payload of 114 bytes. At the end of each
 859 frame of EH-DQ, the coordinator broadcasts a FBP with
 860 a payload of 24 bytes that informs about the length
 861 of the CRQ and the DTQ, the status of the contention
 862 slots, and the number of collision-free slots reserved in
 863 every contention slot. All the packets are composed of a
 864 physical layer preamble, a MAC header, a payload and
 865 a cyclic redundancy code (CRC) of 2 bytes.

866 The system parameters used to evaluate the perfor-
 867 mance are summarized in Table I. They have been se-
 868 lected according to the IEEE 802.15.4 standard [33] and
 869 from the specifications of the CC2520 radio transceiver
 870 [34]. The values of energy consumption have been com-
 871 puted by using the energy consumption model described
 872 in Section 5. In particular, the energy consumed by an
 873 end-device when transmits an ARS packet in one frame,
 874 $E_{ARS} = 1\delta = 143 \mu\text{Joule}$, has been calculated from
 875 Equation (4), and the energy consumed by an end-device
 876 when transmits a data packet in one frame, $E_{data} = 4\delta$,
 877 has been calculated from Equation (6).

$$\mathbb{E}[N_d(l)] = \sum_{d=1}^{N-K} \sum_{e=d+K}^N \pi_{e,1}^B \prod_{i=1}^{d-1} (1 - p_{s,i}) p_{s,d} \cdot \min\left(l, \lfloor \frac{e-d}{K} \rfloor\right). \quad (21)$$

$$J_t = \frac{\mathbb{E}[N_S] T_{data}}{(\mathbb{E}[N_E] + \mathbb{E}[N_S]) (mT_{ARS} + T_{data} + T_{FBP})}, \quad (22)$$

878 Each end-device includes an energy harvester and
 879 an ESD with $N = 40$ energy units δ of capacity. We
 880 assume that the energy harvested by an end-device in
 881 a DCR follows a binomial distribution with probability
 882 mass function

$$q_j = \binom{N_H}{j} \left(\frac{\overline{E_H}}{N_H}\right)^j \left(1 - \frac{\overline{E_H}}{N_H}\right)^{N_H-j} \quad (24)$$

883 for $j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N_H\}$, where $N_H = 40$ is the
 884 maximum number of energy units that can be captured
 885 and $\overline{E_H} \in [0, \dots, N_H]$ is the average number of energy
 886 units harvested per DCR, i.e., the energy harvesting rate.

887 Results for EH-DQ have been obtained analytically
 888 and through computer-based simulations using MAT-
 889 LAB*. The results of 1000 simulation samples have
 890 been averaged for each test case. The tight match
 891 between analytic and simulation results validate the
 892 accuracy of the analytic model proposed in Section 7.

893 In TDMA and EH-RDFSAs, we consider that an end-
 894 device consumes $K = 4$ energy units δ when transmits
 895 a data packet in one frame. We consider an ideal EH-
 896 RDFSAs where the number of contenders per frame is
 897 perfectly estimated and the number of contention slots
 898 is adjusted in every frame to be equal to the number of
 899 end-devices that contend in order to transmit their first
 900 data packet, i.e., $\rho = 1$. Results for TDMA and EH-
 901 RDFSAs have been obtained through computer-based
 902 simulations.

*The MATLAB simulation source code is available from the authors upon request. Please contact the corresponding author in case you are interested in obtaining it to reproduce the paper results and/or extend the simulations.

Table I. System parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
MAC header	8 bytes	Data-rate	250 kbps
Data payload	114 bytes	T_{data}	4.1 ms
ARS payload	1 byte	T_{ARS}	512 μ s
FBP payload	24 bytes	T_{FBP}	1.2 ms
ρ_{tx}	100.8 mW	ρ_{stby}	525 μ W
ρ_{rx}	66.9 mW	ρ_{sleep}	90 nW
E_{ARS}	1δ	E_{data}	4δ

903 8.2. Energy Threshold

904 The DDR and the time efficiency for EH-DQ, EH-
 905 RDFSAs and TDMA are represented in Figure 7a and
 906 Figure 7b, respectively, as a function of the energy
 907 threshold ε_{thr} by considering $\overline{E_H} \in \{10, 20\}$ and $m \in$
 908 $\{3, 10\}$, where m is the number of contention slots
 909 in one frame of EH-DQ. As it can be observed, the
 910 value of the DDR for EH-DQ, EH-RDFSAs and TDMA
 911 increases with the energy harvesting rate. Indeed, the
 912 higher the number of energy units available in the ESDs,
 913 the higher the number of end-devices that become active
 914 in a DCR and the higher the number of possible packet
 915 transmissions.

916 Recall that an end-device becomes active at the
 917 beginning of a DCR if the energy available in its ESD
 918 is above ε_{thr} energy units, and in EH-DQ an end-device
 919 consumes 1 energy unit when it transmits an ARS, and
 920 $K = 4$ energy units when it transmits a data packet.
 921 As shown in Figure 6b, the average number of frames
 922 in which an end-device has to contend until succeeds
 923 in transmitting an ARS, $\mathbb{E}[d]$ (14), is close to 5, 4,
 924 or 3 frames when $n = 1000$ and m is 5, 10, or 20
 925 slots, respectively. Therefore, an end-device consumes
 926 an average of $\mathbb{E}[d]$ energy units in the transmission of
 927 ARS packets. Consequently, an end-device will need at
 928 least an energy level of $\varepsilon_{thr} \simeq \mathbb{E}[d] + KL$ in its ESD at
 929 the beginning of a DCR in order to maximize the DDR.
 930 As it can be observed in Figure 7a, the optimum value
 931 of ε_{thr} that maximizes the DDR for EH-DQ is within
 932 20-25 energy units when m is 3 or 10 slots, $n = 1000$
 933 end-devices, and $L = 5$ data packets.

934 The DDR for EH-RDFSAs increases with the energy
 935 threshold, but much more slightly than in EH-DQ.
 936 This is due to the fact that in EH-RDFSAs, since we
 937 consider that the number of contention slots per frame
 938 is adjusted to be equal to the number of end-devices
 939 that contend in every frame, the probability that an
 940 end-device succeeds in a given frame of EH-RDFSAs
 941 is approximately constant (≈ 0.36) for all the frames.
 942 However, as it can be observed in Figure 6a, in EH-
 943 DQ the probability that an end-device succeeds in
 944 transmitting an ARS is very low in the first levels of the
 945 contention tree and then it increases above 0.36 when
 946 the level number increases. For example, when $m = 10$
 947 slots and $n = 10 \cdot m$ end-devices, the probability that

948 an end-device succeeds in one frame of level 2 and 3 is
949 0.4 and 0.9, respectively.

950 While the DDR for EH-DQ and EH-RDFSA
951 increases with the energy threshold until it reaches its
952 maximum value, results show that the DDR for TDMA
953 does not increase with the energy threshold. This is due
954 to the fact that in TDMA there is no energy waste in
955 collisions and thus the DDR for TDMA only depends
956 on the energy harvesting rate.

957 Finally, as it can be observed in Figure 7a, the
958 DDR for EH-DQ, EH-RDFSA and TDMA decays
959 dramatically when the energy threshold increases above
960 a certain value. Indeed, when the energy threshold is too
961 high, the activation probability decreases, thus reducing
962 the DDR.

963 As it can be observed in Figure 7b, the time efficiency
964 for EH-DQ decreases as the number m of contention
965 slots increases. This is due to the fact that once all the
966 end-devices have succeeded in transmitting their ARS,
967 the higher the number of contention slots per frame,
968 the higher the overhead and the time wasted in the DCR. In
969 addition, as it could be expected according to Equation
970 (23), the time efficiency for EH-DQ is insensitive to the
971 energy harvesting rate and the energy threshold.

972 In contrast, the time efficiency for TDMA decreases
973 as the energy threshold increases. This is due to the
974 fact that the higher the energy threshold, the lower the
975 number of end-devices that become active in a DCR, the
976 higher the number of empty slots, and thus the lower the
977 time efficiency. The time efficiency for TDMA increases
978 as the energy harvesting rate increases. Indeed, the
979 higher the energy harvesting rate, the higher the energy
980 available in the ESDs at the beginning of a DCR, and the
981 higher the number of possible packet transmissions per
982 end-device. Consequently, the probability that one slot
983 in every frame of TDMA contains one successful data
984 packet increases with the energy harvesting rate.

985 Similarly, the time efficiency using EH-RDFSA
986 increases with the energy harvesting rate and the energy
987 threshold. Indeed, the probability that one reserved slot
988 in every frame of EH-RDFSA contains one successful
989 data packet increases with the energy available in the
990 ESDs at the beginning of a DCR.

991 8.3. Number of Contention Slots

992 The DDR and the time efficiency of EH-DQ are
993 represented in Figure 8a and Figure 8b, respectively, as
994 a function of the number m of contention slots (from
995 2 to 20 slots) by considering $\overline{E_H} \in \{5, 10, 20, 30\}$ and
996 $\varepsilon_{thr} = 20$, which is a value of the energy threshold
997 close to the one that maximizes the DDR and the time
998 efficiency for EH-DQ, EH-RDFSA and TDMA, as it can
999 be observed in Figure 7a and Figure 7b. Recall that in
1000 EH-RDFSA the number of contention slots per frame is
1001 adjusted to be equal to the number of contenders in every
1002 frame, and in TDMA the number of slots is equal to the
1003 total number of end-devices in the network.

1004 Results show that the DDR for EH-DQ increases
1005 when the number of contention slots per frame
1006 increases. Indeed, the higher the number of contention
1007 slots, the lower the probability that an ARS collides in
1008 a given frame, and the lower the energy wasted in re-
1009 transmissions, thus increasing the DDR.

1010 The DDR for EH-DQ and EH-RDFSA increases
1011 with the energy harvesting rate. Indeed, the higher the
1012 number of energy units available in the ESDs, the higher
1013 the number of end-devices that become active in a
1014 DCR and the higher the number of possible packet re-
1015 transmissions.

1016 As it can be observed in Figure 8a, EH-DQ can
1017 outperform EH-RDFSA in terms of DDR, for any
1018 energy harvesting rate, if the number of slots per frame
1019 in EH-DQ is properly adjusted. For example, if $n =$
1020 1000 and $\overline{E_H} \in \{5, 10, 20, 30\}$, then the value of m in
1021 EH-DQ must be equal or greater than 3 slots.

1022 As it can be observed in Figure 8b, the time
1023 efficiency for EH-DQ is maximized for 2-3 contention
1024 slots, $J_t \approx 0.80$, and it is degraded as the number of
1025 contention slots per frame increases. Indeed, the higher
1026 the number of contention slots, the higher the time
1027 wasted in every frame once all the end-devices have
1028 succeeded in transmitting their ARS, thus reducing the
1029 time efficiency. In addition, EH-DQ can outperform
1030 EH-RDFSA and TDMA in terms of time efficiency if
1031 the number of contention slots is low, and the time
1032 efficiency for EH-DQ is very similar for different energy
1033 harvesting rates.

1034 There is a trade-off between DDR and time efficiency
1035 for EH-DQ. When the number of contention slots
1036 per frame increases, more end-devices can eventually
1037 succeed in transmitting ARS packets to the coordinator
1038 in a DCR, thus increasing the DDR, at the cost of
1039 reducing the time efficiency and the data collection rate.
1040 However, as it can be observed in Figure 8a, with low
1041 (e.g., 5) and high (e.g., 30) energy harvesting rates,
1042 EH-DQ can be configured with a very low number
1043 of contention slots (e.g., $m = 3$), at almost no cost
1044 in the DDR, and increase the time efficiency to a
1045 certain value close to the maximum. However, with
1046 intermediate energy harvesting rates (e.g., between 10
1047 and 20 energy units), EH-DQ must be configured with a
1048 number of contention slots per frame which depends on
1049 the harvesting rate.

1050 8.4. Energy Harvesting Rate

1051 The DDR and the time efficiency for EH-DQ, EH-
1052 RDFSA and TDMA are represented in Figure 9b and
1053 Figure 9a, respectively, as a function of the energy
1054 harvesting rate $\overline{E_H}$ by considering $m \in \{3, 10\}$ and
1055 $\varepsilon_{thr} = 20$, which is a value of the energy threshold
1056 close to the one that maximizes the DDR and the time
1057 efficiency for EH-DQ, EH-RDFSA and TDMA, as it can
1058 be observed in Figure 7a and Figure 7b.

Figure 7. Data Delivery Ratio and Time Efficiency over the energy threshold using EH-DQ, EH-RDFSFA and TDMA.

Figure 8. Data Delivery Ratio and Time Efficiency over over the number of contention slots per frame.

Figure 9. Data Delivery Ratio and Time Efficiency over the energy harvesting rate using EH-DQ, EH-RDFSFA and TDMA.

1059 The value of the DDR increases almost linearly with
 1060 $\overline{E_H}$ for EH-DQ, EH-RDFSFA, and TDMA. Indeed, the
 1061 higher the energy available in an ESD at the beginning
 1062 of a DCR, the higher the number of possible packet
 1063 transmissions and thus the value of the DDR. As it
 1064 could be expected, TDMA yields a value of DDR equal
 1065 to 1 when $\overline{E_H} \geq 4L = 20$ energy units. Indeed, since
 1066 there are no collisions in TDMA, its performance is
 1067 only limited by the amount of harvested energy and
 1068 the capacity of the ESD. Note that ideal TDMA could
 1069 be considered as the upper bound for random access
 1070 protocols in terms of absence of collisions. In EH-
 1071 RDFSFA, however, the value of the DDR is close to

1072 1 when $\overline{E_H} > 5L$. In its turn, EH-DQ attains a value
 1073 of the DDR equal to 1 when $\overline{E_H} \geq 5L = 25$ energy
 1074 units for $m = 10$, and when $\overline{E_H} \geq 6L = 30$ for $m = 3$.
 1075 Indeed, as the probability of collision is lower when
 1076 the number of contention slots increases, the energy
 1077 consumption due to re-transmissions of ARS packets is
 1078 reduced, thus increasing the DDR. In addition, it can be
 1079 observed that EH-DQ outperforms the DDR provided by
 1080 EH-RDFSFA. Indeed, as in EH-DQ the end-devices only
 1081 contend to transmit short ARS packets, the collisions
 1082 and the energy consumption due to re-transmissions are
 1083 reduced with respect to EH-RDFSFA, thus increasing
 1084 the DDR. Furthermore, the tree splitting algorithm of

1085 EH-DQ allows that the ARS packets can be eventually
1086 transmitted with a finite number of re-transmissions.
1087 Results show that EH-DQ with $m = 10$ requires lower
1088 energy harvesting rate than EH-RDFSFA to get the same
1089 DDR. For example, while EH-RDFSFA requires $\overline{E}_H =$
1090 30 energy units to obtain $\text{DDR} = 0.95$ with $L = 5$, EH-
1091 DQ requires $\overline{E}_H = 23$, which means a reduction of 23%
1092 in energy harvesting rate. Consequently, EH-DQ allows
1093 reducing the total time between consecutive DCRs and
1094 thus increases the network throughput with respect to
1095 EH-RDFSFA.

1096 As it can be observed in Figure 9a, the time efficiency
1097 for TDMA increases with \overline{E}_H and tends to its maximum
1098 value when $\overline{E}_H > 4L$. Indeed, the higher the energy
1099 harvesting rate, the higher the energy available in the
1100 ESDs at the beginning of a DCR, and the higher
1101 the number of possible packet transmissions per end-
1102 device. Consequently, the probability that one slot in
1103 every frame of TDMA contains one successful data
1104 packet increases with \overline{E}_H . In EH-RDFSFA, the time
1105 efficiency increases slightly with \overline{E}_H . Contrarily, the
1106 time efficiency of EH-DQ is insensitive to the energy
1107 harvesting rate.

1108 While the time efficiency in TDMA increases linearly
1109 up to 0.9, which indicates that every slot contains one
1110 successful data packet, the maximum time efficiency
1111 in EH-RDFSFA is 0.7, and it is 0.72 and 0.45 in EH-
1112 DQ with $m = 3$ and $m = 10$ number of contention
1113 slots, respectively. Indeed, while in TDMA each end-
1114 device transmits in its reserved slot, in EH-RDFSFA
1115 and EH-DQ the end-devices have to contend until they
1116 succeed in transmitting their first data packet and the
1117 ARS, respectively, with the consequent waste of time in
1118 contention slots.

1119 When the energy harvesting rate is below a certain
1120 threshold, the time efficiency in EH-DQ is greater
1121 than in TDMA. As it can be observed in Figure 9a,
1122 EH-DQ outperforms TDMA when $\overline{E}_H < 3L$. Indeed,
1123 while the number of slots per frame in TDMA is
1124 constant, equal to the total number of end-devices in
1125 the network regardless of the number of active end-devices,
1126 every frame in EH-DQ contains a very short contention
1127 window and 1 collision-free slot reserved for a specific
1128 end-device, thus leading to higher time efficiency.

9. CONCLUSIONS

1129 In this paper, we have proposed a new MAC protocol,
1130 named Energy Harvesting-aware Distributed Queuing
1131 Access (EH-DQ), for data collection networks where
1132 each end-device is equipped with an energy harvester
1133 and generates messages which are fragmented into small
1134 data packets to be transmitted to a gateway. We have
1135 considered the data delivery ratio (DDR) and the time
1136 efficiency as performance metrics. We have modeled
1137 the operation of EH-DQ with a discrete-time Markov

1138 chain to analyze the evolution of the energy availability
1139 and to calculate the performance metrics. We have
1140 compared the performance of EH-DQ with the EH-
1141 aware Reservation Dynamic Frame Slotted-ALOHA
1142 (EH-RDFSFA) and the upper-bound performance of an
1143 ideal TDMA protocol. Results show that the DDR
1144 increases with the energy harvesting rate for all cases.
1145 EH-DQ and TDMA provide the maximum $\text{DDR} = 1$,
1146 and both outperform EH-RDFSFA in terms of DDR and
1147 time efficiency. While the time efficiency of TDMA
1148 increases with the energy harvesting rate, the time
1149 efficiency of EH-DQ is insensitive to the harvesting
1150 rate. EH-DQ outperforms TDMA in terms of the time
1151 efficiency in a certain range of the energy harvesting
1152 rate which depends on the number of data packets to be
1153 transmitted by each end-device. Furthermore, while EH-
1154 RDFSFA requires to estimate the number of contenders
1155 in each frame to adapt the frame length dynamically,
1156 EH-DQ uses a short and fixed frame length. In addition,
1157 while TDMA requires to update the knowledge of the
1158 network topology to maintain a collision-free schedule,
1159 EH-DQ does not require topology knowledge, thus
1160 reducing overhead and energy consumption. Taking that
1161 into account, we believe that EH-DQ is an interesting
1162 alternative for data collection scenarios with energy
1163 harvesting. Future work aims at including transmission
1164 errors and capture effect in the analysis presented in this
1165 paper.

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REFERENCES

- 1172 1. A. Bachir, M. Dohler, T. Watteyne, K. K. Leung,
1173 Mac essentials for wireless sensor networks, *IEEE*
1174 *Communications Surveys Tutorials* 12 (2) (2010)
1175 222–248. doi:10.1109/SURV.2010.020510.00058.
- 1176 2. G. Anastasi, M. Conti, M. Di Francesco,
1177 A. Passarella, Energy conservation in
1178 wireless sensor networks: A survey, *Ad*
1179 *Hoc Networks* 7 (3) (2009) 537–568.
1180 doi:10.1016/j.adhoc.2008.06.003.
1181 URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2008.06.003)
1182 [adhoc.2008.06.003](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2008.06.003)
- 1183 3. B. Martinez, M. Montn, I. Vilajosana, J. D.
1184 Prades, The power of models: Modeling power
1185 consumption for iot devices, *IEEE Sensors Journal*
1186 15 (10) (2015) 5777–5789.

- 1187 4. S. Ulukus, A. Yener, E. Erkip, O. Simeone, 1244
1188 M. Zorzi, P. Grover, K. Huang, Energy harvest- 1245
1189 ing wireless communications: A review of re- 1246
1190 cent advances, *Selected Areas in Communica-* 1247
1191 *tions*, IEEE Journal on 33 (3) (2015) 360–381. 1248
1192 doi:10.1109/JSAC.2015.2391531. 1249
1193 5. B. Martinez, X. Vilajosana, F. Chraim, I. Vila- 1250
1194 josana, K. S. J. Pister, When scavengers meet 1251
1195 industrial wireless, *IEEE Transactions on In-* 1252
1196 *dustrial Electronics* 62 (5) (2015) 2994–3003. 1253
1197 doi:10.1109/TIE.2014.2362891. 1254
1198 6. J. I. Capetanakis, Tree Algorithms for Packet 1255
1199 Broadcast Channels, *IEEE Transactions on Infor-* 1256
1200 *mation Theory* 25 (5) (1979) 505–515. 1257
1201 7. F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, P. Tuset- 1258
1202 Peiro, L. Alonso, Energy performance of 1259
1203 distributed queuing access in machine-to- 1260
1204 machine networks with idle-to-saturation 1261
1205 transitions, in: 2013 IEEE Globecom 1262
1206 Workshops (GC Wkshps), 2013, pp. 867–872. 1263
1207 doi:10.1109/GLOCOMW.2013.6825098. 1264
1208 8. F. Vazquez-Gallego, L. Alonso, J. Alonso-Zarate, 1265
1209 Energy Harvesting-aware Distributed Queuing Ac- 1266
1210 cess for Wireless Machine-to-Machine Networks, 1267
1211 in: in proc. of the IEEE GLOBECOM 2016, Wash- 1268
1212 ington DC, USA, 2016. 1269
1213 9. W. Xu, G. Campbell, A Near Perfect Stable 1270
1214 Random Access Protocol for a Broadcast Chan- 1271
1215 nel, in: IEEE International Conference on Com- 1272
1216 munications (ICC), Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 370–374. 1273
1217 doi:10.1109/ICC.1992.268230. 1274
1218 10. W. Chien-Ting, G. Campbell, Extended DQRAP 1275
1219 (XDQRAP). A cable TV protocol functioning as 1276
1220 a distributed switch, in: International Workshop 1277
1221 on Community Networking Integrated Multimedia 1278
1222 Services to the Home, 1994, pp. 191–198. 1279
1223 doi:10.1109/CN.1994.337349. 1280
1224 11. L. Harn-Jier, G. Campbell, PDQRAP-prioritized 1281
1225 distributed queueing random access protocol, in: 1282
1226 IEEE Conference on Local Computer Networks, 1283
1227 1994, pp. 82–91. doi:10.1109/LCN.1994.386612. 1284
1228 12. W. Chien-Ting, G. Campbell, Interleaved DQRAP 1285
1229 with Global TQ, Dept. of Comp. Sci., Illinois Inst. 1286
1230 of Technology, 1995. 1287
1231 13. L. Alonso, R. Agusti, O. Sallent, A near-optimum 1288
1232 MAC protocol based on the distributed queueing 1289
1233 random access protocol (DQRAP) for a CDMA 1290
1234 mobile communication system, *IEEE Journal on* 1291
1235 *Selected Areas in Communications* 18 (9) (2000) 1292
1236 1701–1718. doi:10.1109/49.872957. 1293
1237 14. J. Alonso-Zarate, C. Verikoukis, E. Kartsakli, 1294
1238 A. Cateura, L. Alonso, A Near-Optimum Cross- 1295
1239 Layered Distributed Queuing Protocol for Wireless 1296
1240 LAN, *IEEE Wireless Communications* 15 (1) 1297
1241 (2008) 48–55. doi:10.1109/MWC.2008.4454704. 1298
1242 15. J. Alonso-Zarate, L. Alonso, C. Skianis, 1299
1243 C. Verikoukis, Analysis of a Distributed Queuing 1300
Medium Access Control Protocol for Cooperative
ARQ, in: IEEE GLOBECOM, 2010, pp. 1–5.
doi:10.1109/GLOCOM.2010.5683302.
16. J. Alonso-Zarate, D. Gregoratti, P. Giotis, C. Verikoukis, L. Alonso, Medium access control priority mechanism for a DQMAN-based wireless network, *IEEE Communications Letters* 13 (7) (2009) 495–497. doi:10.1109/LCOMM.2009.081502.
17. B. Otal, L. Alonso, C. Verikoukis, Energy-Efficiency Analysis of a Distributed Queuing Medium Access Control Protocol for Biomedical Wireless Sensor Networks in Saturation Conditions, *Sensors* 11 (2) (2011) 1277–1296. doi:10.3390/s110201277.
URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/11/2/1277>
18. F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, P. Tuset-Peiro, L. Alonso, Energy Analysis of a Contention Tree-based Access Protocol for Machine-to-Machine Networks with Idle-to-Saturation Traffic Transitions, in: IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), 2014.
19. P. Tuset-Peiro, F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, L. Alonso, X. Vilajosana, Experimental energy consumption of frame slotted ALOHA and distributed queuing for data collection scenarios, *Sensors* 14 (8) (2014) 13416–13436. doi:10.3390/s140813416.
URL <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/14/8/13416>
20. P. Tuset-Peiro, F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, L. Alonso, X. Vilajosana, LPDQ: A self-scheduled TDMA MAC protocol for one-hop dynamic low-power wireless networks, *Pervasive and Mobile Computing* 20 (2015) 84 – 99. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pmcj.2014.09.004.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1574119214001576>
21. P. Tuset-Peiro, L. Alonso, F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, X. Vilajosana-Guillen, Demonstrating low-power distributed queuing for active {RFID} communications at 433 mhz, in: 2014 IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS), 2014, pp. 157–158. doi:10.1109/INFOCOMW.2014.6849203.
22. M. Moradian, F. Ashtiani, Throughput analysis of a slotted aloha-based network with energy harvesting nodes, in: IEEE PIMRC, 2012, pp. 351–356. doi:10.1109/PIMRC.2012.6362809.
23. G. Yang, G.-Y. Lin, H.-Y. Wei, Markov chain performance model for IEEE 802.11 devices with energy harvesting source, in: IEEE GLOBECOM, 2012, pp. 5212–5217. doi:10.1109/GLOCOM.2012.6503948.
24. F. Iannello, O. Simeone, P. Popovski, U. Spagnolini, Energy group-based dynamic framed

- 1301 ALOHA for wireless networks with energy har-
1302 vesting, in: Annual Conference on Information
1303 Sciences and Systems (CISS), 2012, pp. 1–6.
1304 doi:10.1109/CISS.2012.6310797.
- 1305 25. O. Briante, A. M. Mandalari, A. Molinaro,
1306 G. Ruggeri, F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate,
1307 Duty-Cycle Optimization for Machine-to-Machine
1308 Area Networks based on Frame Slotted-ALOHA
1309 with Energy Harvesting Capabilities, in: European
1310 Wireless, 2014.
- 1311 26. F. Iannello, O. Simeone, U. Spagnolini, Medium
1312 Access Control Protocols for Wireless Sensor Net-
1313 works with Energy Harvesting, *IEEE Transactions*
1314 *on Communications* 60 (5) (2012) 1381–1389.
1315 doi:10.1109/TCOMM.2012.030712.110089.
- 1316 27. F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, S. Wu,
1317 Y. Chen, K. Chai, Analysis and performance eval-
1318 uation of dynamic frame slotted-ALOHA in wire-
1319 less Machine-to-Machine networks with energy
1320 harvesting, in: IEEE GLOBECOM Workshop on
1321 Green Broadband Access, 2014.
- 1322 28. F. Vazquez-Gallego, J. Alonso-Zarate, L. Alonso,
1323 Reservation Dynamic Frame Slotted-ALOHA for
1324 Wireless M2M Networks with Energy Harvesting,
1325 in: IEEE International Conference on Communica-
1326 tions (ICC), 2015.
- 1327 29. P. Lee, Z. A. Eu, M. Han, H. Tan, Empirical
1328 modeling of a solar-powered energy harvesting
1329 wireless sensor node for time-slotted operation,
1330 in: Wireless Communications and Networking
1331 Conference (WCNC), 2011 IEEE, 2011, pp. 179–
1332 184. doi:10.1109/WCNC.2011.5779157.
- 1333 30. C. K. Ho, P. D. Khoa, P. C. Ming, Markovian
1334 models for harvested energy in wireless communi-
1335 cations, in: Communication Systems (ICCS), 2010
1336 IEEE International Conference on, 2010, pp. 311–
1337 315. doi:10.1109/ICCS.2010.5686445.
- 1338 31. M. Gorlatova, A. Wallwater, G. Zussman, Net-
1339 working low-power energy harvesting devices:
1340 Measurements and algorithms, in: INFOCOM,
1341 2011 Proceedings IEEE, 2011, pp. 1602–1610.
1342 doi:10.1109/INFOCOM.2011.5934952.
- 1343 32. J. Norris, Markov Chains, Cambridge Series in Sta-
1344 tistical and Probabilistic Mathematics, Cambridge
1345 University Press, 1998.
- 1346 33. IEEE Std., IEEE Std 802.15.4-2006: Wireless
1347 Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical
1348 Layer (PHY) Specifications for Low-Rate Wireless
1349 Personal Area Networks (WPANs) (September
1350 2006).
- 1351 34. CC2520 datasheet.
1352 URL [http://www.ti.com/lit/ds/
1353 symlink/cc22520.pdf](http://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/cc22520.pdf)